

COLORIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF CHLORAL (HYDRATE)

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The Fujiwara colour reaction has been extended to the estimation of chloral (hydrate). Different factors influencing the intensity and stability of colour have been studied. The intensity of colour exhibits a linear relationship with the amount of chloral (hydrate). The method is free from interference by common impurities in chloral hydrate.

The Fujiwara colour reaction between chloroform, pyridine and strong alkalis at 100° (*Sitzungsber. Abhandl. naturforsch. Ges. Rostock*, 1914, 6, 1) was found by Ross to be a general test for compounds with -C (halogen)₂ moiety (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1923, 88, 641). Various workers applied this reaction for the colorimetric estimation of chloroform and carbon tetrachloride in blood and tissues of animals, air and soil (Cole, *ibid.*, 1926, 71, 173; Gettler and Blume, *Arch. Path.*, 1931, 11, 554; Daroga and Pollard, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1941, 60, 218; Adams, *J. Pharmacol.*, 1942, 74, 11; Kulkarni, *Curr. Sci.*, 1943, 12, 324; *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1944, 32, 189; Ussing, *Acta Physiol. Scand.*, 1945, 9, 214; Habgood and Powell, *Brit. J. Ind. Med.*, 1945, 2, 39; Webb, Kay and Nichol, *J. Ind. Hyg. Toxicol.*, 1945, 27, 249). As chloral contains the -C (halogen)₂ group and is known to be readily and quantitatively hydrolysed to chloroform, it has been thought of interest to extend this method to the estimation of chloral (cf. Friedman and Calderone, *J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1934, 19, 1332).

Previous workers showed that with chloroform or carbon tetrachloride, best results were obtained with 20% NaOH and that a brighter colour was produced in the presence of acetone (Daroga and Pollard, *loc.cit.*). These conditions have been found satisfactory and therefore maintained in the following experiments. The colour was ordinarily unstable, but could be stabilised for a longer period by cooling and separating the coloured pyridine layer, although different orders of stability have been reported by different workers. Similarly, several different periods of heating have been recommended in the literature. The present studies were therefore carried out with reference to the following variants :

- (i) The influence of heating time on colour intensity.
- (ii) The stability of red colour after separating the coloured pyridine layer.
- (iii) The variation of colour intensity with the amount of chloral hydrate using technical and pure pyridine.
- (iv) The influence of impurities in chloral on colour intensity.

A heating time of 5 minutes was found to be optimum and the colour was stable for over one hour. There was straight line relationship between the quantity of chloral and the colour intensity with technical as well as pure pyridine; the latter, however, exhibited a more intense colour and was therefore more suited when very small quantities of chloral were to be estimated. Such common impurities as hydrochloric acid, ethanol and dichloroacetaldehyde did not interfere with the reaction.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Influence of Heating Time on Colour Intensity.—A mixture of 5 c.c. of 40% NaOH* solution, 10 c.c. of colorless technical pyridine bases (b.p. 115°-40°), 2 c.c. of acetone and 5 c.c. of aqueous test solution (2.42 mg. of CCl_3CHO , H_2O) was heated with shaking in a 50 c.c. r.b. flask, plugged with cotton wool on a boiling water-bath for varying intervals of time (2-6 mins.). After cooling under tap water (about 20°) for 1-2 minutes, the coloured pyridine layer was separated and diluted with acetone to 20 c.c. in a measuring flask. A 10 mm layer of this solution was matched against glass standards in a Lovibond tintometer. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Time of heating (mins.)	...	2	3	4	5	6	
Reading	{ Red	...	4.5	4.6	4.9	4.9	4.9
	{ Brightness	...	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2

The colour intensity being maximum at 4-6 minutes, an optimum heating time of 5 minutes was therefore adopted for the subsequent experiments.

Stability of Red Colour.—The above experiment was repeated with a heating time of 5 minutes and the final diluted coloured solution matched as before in the tintometer at different intervals of time (Table II).

TABLE II

Time after separation (mins.)	...	5	15	30	60	120	180	
Reading	{ Red	...	4.9	4.9	4.9	4.9	4.6	4.3
	{ Brightness	...	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.2

Thus, the colour was stable for more than one hour. A more thorough separation by settling the pyridine layer for a longer period did not improve the stability. It only exhibited a brighter colour (brightness 0.4), probably due to a more complete removal of suspended globules of alkali solution from the pyridine layer.

Variation of Colour Intensity with the amount of Chloral Hydrate.—To 40% NaOH (5 c.c.), colorless technical pyridine bases (b.p. 115-40°; 10 c.c.) and acetone (2 c.c.) in a 50 c.c. r.b. flask were added varying amounts (i) (0.5-5.0 c.c.) of chloral hydrate solution (0.9680 mg./c.c.) and (ii) water (4.5-0.0 c.c.) so that the total volume of (i) and (ii) added was always 5 c.c. The reaction mixture was treated as before and a 10 mm depth of the final diluted coloured solution matched in the tintometer. The results have been summarised in Table III and represented in Fig. 1.

* The total volume of aqueous layer (5 c.c. NaOH + 5 c.c. test solution) came to 10 c.c. so that the final solution was 20% NaOH.

TABLE III

With tech. pyridine bases (b.p. 115–40°).
Tot 1 vol. added = 5.0 c.c.

S. No.	Chloral hydrate added.		Water added.	Tintometer reading.	
	Soln.	Amount.		Red.	Brightness.
1	0.5 c.c.	0.484 mg.	4.5 c.c.	0.9	0.2
2	1.0	0.968	4.0	1.9	0.2
3	1.5	1.452	3.5	2.7	0.2
4	2.0	1.936	3.0	3.8	0.2
5	2.5	2.420	2.5	4.8	0.2
6	3.0	2.904	2.0	5.8	0.2
7	3.5	3.388	1.5	6.7	0.2
8	4.0	3.872	1.0	7.6	0.2
9	4.5	4.356	0.5	8.6	0.2
10	5.0	4.840	0.0	9.5	0.2

A similar set of experiments was carried out with chemically pure pyridine (b.p. 112–14°) taking 1.5 c.c. of a weaker solution of chloral hydrate (0.1936 mg./c.c.) because the above stronger solution gave large values of intensities (more than 20 Lovibond units) with pure pyridine (Table IV, Fig. 1).

TABLE IV

With chemically pure pyridine.
Total vol. added = 5.0 c.c.

S. No.	Chloral hydrate added.		Water added.	Tintometer reading	
	Soln.	Amount.		Red.	Brightness.
1	1.0 c.c.	0.1936 mg.	4.0 c.c.	1.3	0.1
2	2.0	0.3872	3.0	2.6	0.1
3	3.0	0.5808	2.0	3.9	0.1
4	4.0	0.7744	1.0	5.2	0.1
5	5.0	0.9680	0.0	6.5	0.1

The Influence of Impurities on Colour Intensity.—Several experiments were performed with 2–3 mg. of chloral hydrate when present alone and also in mixtures with 1–4 mg. of dichloroacetaldehyde, 10–20 mg. of HCl and 20–40 mg. of ethanol. The colour intensity was not affected by any one or all of these impurities.

The colour produced by heating chloral hydrate with NaOH and pyridine has maximum intensity for a heating time of 4–6 minutes and can be stabilised for more than one hour by cooling and separating the coloured pyridine layer; it is quantitatively reproducible. On plotting the intensity of red colour against the amount of chloral hydrate, a straight line is obtained with technical as well as pure pyridine, indicating the applicability of Beer's law to the system (Fig. 1). The common impurities such as dichloroacetaldehyde, hydrochloric acid and ethanol do not interfere.

FIG. 1

For equal quantities of chloral hydrate, however, a more intense colour is developed with pure pyridine than with the technical variety (e.g. 6.5 and 1.9 Lovibond red units respectively for 0.9680 mg. of $\text{CCl}_3\text{CHO}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$, cf. Fig. 1). This is in conformity with an earlier observation of Daroga and Pollard (*loc.cit.*) that with CHCl_3 or CCl_4 the colour developed is a function of the amount of pyridine added. Thus, whereas both technical and pure pyridine can be used for this estimation, the latter is preferable when very small amounts of chloral are to be estimated.

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